

EFFICACY OF NATURAL EXTRACTS AS IRRIGANTS IN SMEAR LAYER REMOVAL – SEM ANALYSIS : AN INVITRO STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction : Chemo-mechanical preparation is essential for successful endodontic treatment and relies on effective instruments and irrigating solutions. Irrigants help dissolve organic tissue, prevent debris accumulation, and remove smear layer. Due to the limitations and safety concerns of synthetic irrigants, herbal alternatives with healing properties may offer a safer and effective option in endodontic therapy.

Aim : The present study aimed to assess the effect of neem leaf extract, pomegranate extract and Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) on smear layer removal by using Scanning Electron Microscope.

Materials and Methodology : Sixty human mandibular single rooted premolars were decoronated to a root length of 15mm. They were cleaned and shaped upto 40k size file using saline as an irrigant throughout the instrumentation. The specimens were equally divided into 3 groups according to final irrigant used for smear layer evaluation; group 1 - Neem solution, group 2 - Pomegranate solution, group 3 - 17% EDTA. Samples were split longitudinally and examined under microscope for smear layer evaluation at apical thirds. The analysis was done using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Kruskal–Wallis test.

Result : Pomegranate solution demonstrated the maximum efficiency in eliminating the smear layer than EDTA and Neem solution.

Conclusion : Neem and Pomegranate both showed the potential to eliminate the smear layer. Pomegranate solution demonstrated the maximum efficiency in eliminating the smear layer.

Keyword : Pomegranate, Neem, EDTA, Smear layer, SEM

INTRODUCTION :

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) is a powerful imaging tool that reveals precise surface characteristics such as texture, particle shape and size, composition, and crystallographic information of an object. It was chosen because it provides detailed three-dimensional and topographical images of the prepared root canal.^[3]

The primary cause of endodontic failure is persistence of pathogens due to the complex anatomy of root canals.^[4] Effective endodontic treatment requires complete removal and disinfection of microorganisms and their byproducts from the infected canal system.^[9] While canal shaping contributes to this process, the primary role is played by antimicrobial irrigants. During the complete debridement of root canals, smear layer removal is important.^[3] Moreover, it can compromise the sealing ability and adaptation of root canal obturating materials.^[9]

The use of plants for healing is a practice rooted in ancient traditions, now witnessing a resurgence in modern times. Herbal products have been proven to be safe and contain active constituents that exert physiological effects in addition to their curative properties.^[1] Recently, some authors have focused on use of natural extracts as biological smear layer-removing agents, aiming to reduce the risk factors associated with chemical irrigants like ineffectiveness, increased antimicrobial resistance, tissue reactions and alterations in the mechanical properties of radicular dentin.^[6] Thus, two herbal alternatives which might disinfect the root canal system were selected namely, Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract, Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) peel extract so as to analyse its efficacy to remove smear layer.^{[1][8]}

The neem plant (*Azadirachta indica*) contains a group of isoprenoid compounds—including nimbin, nimbinin, nimbidinin, nimbolide, and nimbidic acid—which possess wide range of therapeutic and antibacterial properties. These bioactive constituents contribute to neem's potential application as an endodontic irrigant. Notably, neem exhibits excellent biocompatibility and strong antioxidant activity, thereby minimizing the risk of tissue toxicity. Furthermore, neem extract has demonstrated effectiveness in the removal of smear layers from the apical section of the root canal system, supporting its use as a natural and efficient irrigating agent in endodontic procedures.^{[1][3]} *Punica granatum* (Pomegranate) exhibits antibacterial, antioxidant, radical scavenging ability and chelating potency.^[8]

Although research in this field is on the rise, there is still limited literature evaluating the efficacy of these products as endodontic irrigants for smear layer removal. Hence, the purpose of this study was to assess and compare the smear layer removal efficacy of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) with EDTA in smear layer removal.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY :

A total of 60 freshly extracted, single-rooted, noncarious mandibular premolar teeth were collected, the teeth were extracted due to compromised periodontal health and also for orthodontic purposes. To avoid any anatomical variation and preserve standardization, straight single canal and single-rooted mandibular premolars were selected according to requirements provided by Schneider et al. with a curvature of fewer than 5°. Teeth with developmental anomalies, external resorption, vertical/horizontal root fracture, calcified canals, endodontically treated teeth, deep carious lesions, and malformed teeth were excluded from the study.^[13] Using ultrasonic scaler, debris was cleaned from teeth and stored in 10% formaldehyde till further use. The teeth were decoronated to obtain a uniform working length of 15 mm for all samples using a diamond disc. The apical foramen of each root was sealed using sticky wax so as to restrict the flow of irrigants through it and to simulate the clinical situation.^[3,9] The samples were divided randomly into three groups on the basis of different endodontic irrigants used : Group I : Neem (n= 20), Group II : Pomegranate (n= 20), and Group III : 17 % EDTA liquid (n= 20).

Neem leaf extract – Neem leaf powder was taken and weighed (50 g) mixed with distilled water (500 ml), and then boiled at 100°C so as to get 50 ml of neem leaf extract.^[3] *Punica granatum* (Pomegranate) peels were sun-dried and ground into fine powder. The powders underwent cold maceration, which involved intermittent stirring with a sterile glass rod and being left undisturbed for 48 hours before being filtered through a sterile muslin cloth and heated in a water bath to 110°C to produce crude extracts. And 2.5g of dried pomegranate crude extract is mixed with 20ml of distilled water to obtain 12.5% of *Punica granatum* extract.^[8]

Root canal preparations were done till size # 25 using hand K-files which was followed by Protaper Gold rotary instrumentation up to size F3 with crown down preparation technique at 300 rpm speed and 5.10 N cm torque. During the instrumentation, the root canals were irrigated using 2 ml of the prepared irrigating solution of the respective group for 10 seconds after the use of each file. After instrumentation was complete, final irrigation was done with 2ml of respective irrigant for 2 min for the removal of smear layer. The study samples were subsequently rinsed with sterile distilled water in each group and dried with sterile absorbent paper sheets.

Using a diamond disc, longitudinal grooves were placed on the buccal and lingual surfaces of the root portion of all the samples without penetrating into the root canal. Using chisel, the root portion was split into two halves. One half of each tooth was selected and prepared for SEM examination. All the samples were mounted on an aluminium stub and gold sputter coating was done. The coded specimens were secured on metal stubs, desiccated, sputter coated with 35 nm of gold and examined using a Scanning electron microscope. The apical one-third of root dentin was observed with SEM under 1000X. [3,4,11,12,13]

Smear layer evaluation criteria Score :

The scoring system described by Prado et al. in 2011 was used to evaluate the degree of smear layer removal :

Score 1 : No smear layer & all tubules are clean & open

Score 2 : Few areas covered by smear layer with most tubules cleaned & opened

Score 3 : Smear layer covering almost all surface, with a few tubules opened

Score 4 : Smear layer covering all the surfaces.

Scanning electron microscope images ($\times 1000$) depicting smear layer removal using (a) Neem leaf extract (Group I), (b) Pomegranate extract (Group II), (c) 17% liquid EDTA as irrigants.

RESULT :

The data was obtained and entered in Microsoft Excel version 13. The data subjected to Statistical analysis using IBM Statistical Package for Social Science version 21. For the categorical Scores in Each group Frequency and Percentage was obtained. The Mean Smear Layer Score removal was obtained. Distribution of categorical scores was compared using the Chi-square test. Intergroup comparison of mean scores among Neem, Pomegranate, and EDTA groups was carried out using one-way ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test.

GROUPS		Score 1	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4	Total	p value	p value between groups
	n :	6	7	5	2	20		
Neem	% :	30	35	25	10	100	0.66	
	n :	14	4	2	0	20		
Pomegranate	% :	70	20	10	0	100	0.001	0.027
	n :	4	6	6	4	20		
EDTA	% :	20	30	30	20	100	0.85	
Total	n :	24	17	13	6	60		
	% :					100		

When the Distribution of the Smear Layer Score between Groups was evaluated, it was observed that of the 20 teeth irrigated with pomegranate extract 14 (70%) had no smear layer, EDTA had 4 (20%), Neem had 6 (30%) teeth which had no smear layer with all tubules are clean and open. It was observed that pomegranate extract was more efficacious followed by Neem leaf extract followed by EDTA.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error	P value
Group 1 Neem	20	2.15	0.99	0.22	
Group 2 Pomegranate	20	1.40	0.75	0.17	0.004
Group 3 17% EDTA	20	2.50	1.05	0.23	

The Mean Distribution of the Smear Layer Score was 2.15 ± 0.99 , 1.40 ± 0.75 and 2.50 ± 1.05 . The score was lowest for Pomegranate group indicating a better removal of Smear Layer followed by Neem followed by EDTA and this difference in Mean was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)

DISCUSSION :

The intricate root canal structure makes elimination of micro-organisms problematic. The smear layer being a loosely adherent structure, can harbor bacteria and provide an avenue for leakage & bacterial contamination. Bacteria could be shielded by the smear layer from the actions of antibacterial agents, can survive & multiply. This may offer some explanation for some long or medium term failures of root canal treatments.^[17]

Many chemical substances have been suggested in various studies for root canal disinfection. However, due to the adverse effects, toxicity issues, inability to completely remove the smear layer, growing microbial resistance to the routinely used conventional root canal disinfectants and inability to eliminate the microbes such as *Enterococcus faecalis* which flourish in periapical abscesses and granulomas, causing catastrophe of the endodontic treatment lead to development of alternative modalities. Many herbal products with biological and antimicrobial properties have been studied and recommended for root canal disinfection. The major advantages of using herbal extracts as alternative antimicrobial agents for root canal disinfection are ease of availability of these extracts, cost efficiency, augmented shelf life, low toxicity, and absence of microbial resistance.^[4,7]

The availability of calcium ions from hydroxyapatite for chelation decreases as the pH increases. As a result, a higher dissociation of the acidic irrigant results in greater attraction of calcium ions.^[11,15] The presence of ascorbic acid and flavonoids in these herbal irrigants may be the reason for their efficient removal of the smear layer. *Punica granatum* also exhibits greater smear layer removal because of its slightly acidic pH. (3.25-4.14), which may be the reason for a decreased tendency to reduce microhardness and can be considered an effective endodontic irrigant.^[8,19] The results of this study show that Pomegranate extract and neem leaf extract can be used effectively as an alternative irrigants to conventional ones.

Wolinsky et al. confirmed the inhibitory effects of aqueous extract from *neem* upon bacterial aggregation, growth, adhesion to hydroxyapatite, and production of insoluble glucan, which reduces the smear layer formation.^[20]

Several studies have shown that a neutral EDTA solution can reduce the dentin portion of mineral and non-collagenous proteins (NCPs). Neutral EDTA reduces dentin mineral content and non-collagenous proteins (NCPs) by chelating both free and NCP-bound calcium.^[13,18] Because NCP content is lower in the apical third, EDTA-induced decalcification is reduced in this region, making it less effective apically. For irrigation, 27-gauge side-vented needles were used after instrumentation, as their small bore allows deeper apical penetration while enhancing canal wall contact and minimizing apical extrusion, thereby improving smear layer removal. This increases the irrigant's efficacy in eliminating the smear coating from root canals.^[13]

CONCLUSION :

Within the limitations of this *in vitro* study, it may be concluded that the greatest efficacy of smear layer removal is seen with Pomegranate, followed by Neem thereby followed by EDTA. Today is the era of scientific proof medicine that is any pharmaceutical intended for human use must undergo comprehensive *in vitro* & *in vivo* testing. Herbal products appear promising *in vitro*, but further investigations are recommended to evaluate the potential use of Pomegranate extract as an irrigant.

REFERENCES :

1. A Comparative Evaluation between Neem, Triphala and Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid to Determine Smear Layer Removal Efficacy Using Scanning Electron Microscope –An *in Vitro* Study. *Afr.J.Bio.Sc.* 6(6) (2024) 5978-5987.
2. Chhabra N, Gyanani H, Kamatagi L. Smear layer removal efficacy of combination of herbal extracts in two different ratios either alone or supplemented with sonic agitation: An *in vitro* scanning electron microscope study. *J Conserv Dent* 2015;18:374-8
3. Setia R, Bajaj N, Bhola M, Brar GS. Comparative evaluation of smear layer removal efficacy of neem leaf extract, propolis, and orange oil when used as endodontic irrigants: An *in vitro* scanning electron microscopic study. *Contemporary Clinical Dentistry*. 2023 Apr 1;14(2):128-34.
4. Munaga S, Halkai KR, Al Jarrah AK, Chitumalla R, Halkai R, Khan S. Role of herbal extracts in root canal disinfection and removal of smear layer: a review. *Journal of Chitwan Medical College*. 2022 Jun 30;12(2):130-7.
5. Chamseddine R, Abiad RS. Uses of herbal extracts in endodontology: A literature review. *BAU Journal-Science and Technology*. 2024;5(2):8.
6. Zeid ST, Bastawy HA, Saleh AA. Natural extracts as biological smear layer removing agents: A literature review. *Journal of International Society of Preventive and Community Dentistry*. 2021 Nov 1;11(6):589-600.
7. Ballal NV, Mala K, Bhat KS. Evaluation of the effect of maleic acid and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid on the microhardness and surface roughness of human root canal dentin. *J Endod* 2010;36:1385-8.
8. Lakshmaiah D, Irudayaraj N, Ambeth N, Ramachandran A, Sakthi N, Kumar N. Comparative evaluation of microhardness, smear layer removal efficacy and depth of penetration using *Punica granatum*, *Embolica officinalis* and sodium hypochlorite as endodontic irrigants: an *in vitro* study. *Cureus*. 2023 Sep 6;15(9).
9. Sulgante S, Ghatole K, Indi S, Diwanji P, Hambire A, Thimwala A. Comparative evaluation of smear layer removal ability of herbal endodontic irrigants- SEM study.
10. Mukherjee M, Kalita T, Barua P, Barman A, Thonai S, Mahanta Sr P, Medhi H. Efficacy of smear layer removal of human teeth root canals using herbal and chemical irrigants: an *in vitro* study. *Cureus*. 2023 Jun 15;15(6).
11. Bhargava KY, Aggarwal S, Kumar T, Bhargava S. Comparative evaluation of the efficacy of three anti-oxidants vs. NaOCl and EDTA: Used for root canal irrigation in smear layer removal-SEM study. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2015;7(6):366-71.
12. Rao SA, Sowjanya KI, Sunitha L. Comparison of smear layer removal ability and the effect on root dentin strength of garlic extract and EDTA used as final irrigants—An *in vitro* study. *Indian J Conserv Endod*. 2016 Oct;1:81-5.
13. Mankeliya S, Singhal RK, Gupta A, Pathak VK, Kushwah A. A comparative evaluation of smear layer removal by using four different irrigation solutions like root canal irrigants: An *in vitro* SEM study. *The Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*. 2021 Jul 9;22(5):527-31.

14. Violich DR, Chandler NP. The smear layer in endodontics—a review. *International endodontic journal*. 2010 Jan;43(1):2-15.
15. Jain PA, Tejaswi S, Parinitha MS, Shetty S, Ambikathanaya UK: Comparative evaluation of antibacterial activity of *Punica granatum*, *Acacia nilotica* and *Emblica officinalis* against *Enterococcus faecalis* and their smear layer removal ability when used as endodontic irrigants: an in-vitro study. *Int J Res Rev*. 2019, 6:18494.
16. Badr MM, Elhafez E. Comparison of Antibacterial Effect and Smear Layer Removal of Herbal versus Traditional Irrigants-An in vitro Study. *Egyptian Dental Journal*. 2020 Jul 1;66(3-July (Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics)):1863-71.
17. Jhajharia K, Parolia A, Shetty KV, Mehta LK. Biofilm in endodontics: a review. *Journal of International Society of Preventive and Community Dentistry*. 2015 Jan 1;5(1):1-2.
18. Taneja S, Kumari M, Anand S. Effect of QMix, peracetic acid, and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid on calcium loss and microhardness of root dentine. *J Conserv Dent* 2014;17(2):155–158. DOI: 10.4103/09720707.128058.
19. Shahravan A, Haghdoost AA, Adl A, Rahimi H, Shadifar F: Effect of smear layer on sealing ability of canal obturation: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Endod*. 2007, 33:96-105. 10.1016/j.joen.2006.10.007
20. Wolinsky LE, Mania S, Nachnani S, et al. The inhibiting effect of aqueous *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) extract upon bacterial properties influencing in vitro plaque formation. *J Dent Res*. 1996;75(2):816–822.